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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Openness, Agricultural Credits, and the Agricultural Output in Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the tripartite relationship between openness, credits to the agricultural sector, and agricultural sector output in Nigeria for the period spanning 1981 to 2021. The theoretical underpinnings for this study are the factor proportion model of international trade and the Keynesian Mundell-Fleming IS-LM framework. The time series study adopted the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model as its estimation procedure due to the presence of mixed order of integration in two structural equation models. The first estimation shows that openness, which is proxied by trade openness and foreign direct investment, does not have a significant effect on agricultural output. While the second estimation shows that foreign aid to agriculture has both long and short-run effects on agriculture, commercial bank credit has a long-run effect on agricultural output. The time series study concludes that foreign aid and commercial bank credits are the two channels through which credit to the agricultural sector can be stimulated. Therefore, the study recommends that government should ensure that foreign aid to the sector is used to purchase agricultural inputs that would be delivered directly to farmers, monitor their uses, and make efforts to reduce the devaluation of the local currency as the exchange rate appreciates.

Introduction

Agriculture has been emphasized as a source of human prosperity, food, and raw materials used in manufacturing. According to Lawal et al. (2018), agriculture's role in propelling the nation's economy's growth and development cannot be overstated because it fosters sustainability in economic activities, ensures food security, employs rural dwellers, and reduces poverty, among other things.

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Prior to the arrival of crude oil, agriculture was the mainstay of the Nigerian economy, contributing significantly to the country's overall GDP. Agriculture, which includes agricultural production, animal husbandry, and aquaculture for human use, employs more than half of the population in most developing countries, such as Nigeria. According to Kenny (2019), agricultural expansion is required for most countries to achieve industrialization. The agricultural sector has continued to contribute to developing countries' economies by meeting basic human needs, creating jobs, producing industrial materials for domestic use and export, and contributing foreign earnings (Akinwale, Adekunle, and Obagunwa, 2018). Crop production is the most important sector in Nigeria, accounting for around 87.6% of total output. Cattle, fishing, and forestry come in at 8.1%, 3.2%, and 1.1%, respectively (Erumebor, 2021). A simple ratio analysis of data from the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) monthly bulletin shows that agriculture contributed 23.17% of Nigeria's overall GDP on average between 1981 and 2019, up from 11.77% in 1981 (CBN, 2021). The world's affluent countries have provided various proposals and development guidance, including trade openness, in an attempt to aid developing countries in strengthening their economies and expanding their own trading frontier. Trade openness became prominent as a development policy in 1987, when the World Bank first presented it in its World Development Report. To that purpose, numerous economic theories (neoclassical and new Keynesian) have identified trade openness as the panacea for accelerating the pace of economic progress.

In Nigeria, agriculture employs 70% of the population, and this therefore, means that economic growth will be difficult to attain if the industry is not developed (Odetola and Etumnu, 2013). The Nigerian government has taken various measures to grow her agricultural sector over the years, including, but not limited to accepting the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) in 1986, the Millennium Development Goal (MDG) in 2010, the Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) in 2015, the Economic Recovery and Growth Plan (ERGP) in 2017, the New Economic Partnership for Africa (NEPAD), and National Economic Empowerment and Development (NEED). From a policy standpoint, the federal government implemented: the 1973 National Accelerated Food Production Programme; the elimination of import duties on fishing vessels and agricultural machinery and equipment; the Green Revolution Program; the establishment of the agricultural and cooperative bank limited; the agricultural credit guarantee scheme; the Operation Feed the Nation scheme; and the increase in bank

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loans and advances to the agricultural sector from sixty percent to seventy percent.

In addition, successive Nigerian governments increased agricultural output through the Central Bank of Nigeria's agricultural financing schemes such as the N200 billion Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACCS), which focused on financing large projects along the agricultural value chain, and the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF), which encourages agricultural lending by providing guarantees to commercial banks. Despite initiatives and policies aimed at opening up the economy and increasing agricultural productivity, the bad trend continues. In 2015, the overall proportion of merchandised imported food into Nigeria was 16.94892 percent of total imports. It fell to 12.8506 percent in 2016 before rebounding to 16.31576 percent in 2017, followed by a further drop to 10.93179 percent in 2018, 9.915775 percent in 2019, and 14.62608 percent in 2020. Between the first quarter of 2020 and the fourth quarter of 2021, credit allocated by the bank to private agribusinesses in Nigeria increased. Specifically, loans obtained by this sector increased from approximately 853 billion naira (NGN) to over four trillion NGN. Nonetheless, Nigeria has been coping with food shortages and an increasing population. As a result of the agriculture sector's failure to feed the world's rapidly expanding population, Nigeria's agricultural issues have worsened significantly. The most tangible result of low crop output in Nigeria is a long-term drop in availability and high costs which lead to food inflation. And for farmers, particularly those in rural areas, it may mean a change in livelihood. Nigeria currently has 14.4 million people facing food crisis, which includes those displaced by the country's numerous security difficulties. Low crop output can also lead to a rise in poverty, which can lead to secondary issues such as malnutrition and ill health.

Although there has been an array of empirical literature relating to the effect of trade openness on agriculture in developed and developing countries, there are others that dwell on the effect of bank credit on agriculture as well. A critical evaluation of studies by Muhammad and Atte (2006), Felix, Kolawole, and Musa (2013), Felix, Ukwani, and Martins (2013), and Etuk, Igbodor, and Effiong (2016) revealed that agriculture contributed significantly to the nation's GDP, with a coefficient of 0.664. Ude and Agodi (2015) exposed the fact that trade openness has a positive effect on agricultural sector performance because it boosts the confidence of investors. Further more, the researches by Florence and Nathan (2020); Okafor (2020); Bahşi and Etin

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(2020); Seven and Tumen (2020); Osabohien, Mordi, and Ogundipe (2022) indicated that credit to the agricultural sector has a positive effect on the sector's output as opposed to the negative effect that was estimated by Uremadu, Ehimare, and Okhuebor (2019). As a result, there is no agreement among the studies evaluated, and relying on such a study for policymaking in a vulnerable country like Nigeria would be policy suicide. Furthermore, the reviewed study had a limited view of credit to the agricultural sector because none of the studies were able to incorporate foreign aid and a form of credit to the sector, and there are only a few studies that incorporated trade openness, credit to agriculture, and agricultural sector output in Nigeria from 1980 to 2022.

Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Clarifications

Agriculture:

Agriculture involves the cultivation of land and the rearing of animals for the purpose of producing food for humans, feed for animals, and raw materials for industries. It involves cropping, livestock, forestry, fishing, processing, and marketing of the agricultural product (Anyanwu 2014). Okah (2007) defines agriculture as the cultivation of land and raising animals for the purpose of producing food for man, feed for animals, and raw materials for our industries. According to Akinwala (2018), agriculture is defined as the cultivation of crops, the rearing of animals, and aquaculture for human consumption. It is the science and art of producing crops or animals under the supervision of humans in a specific location (Acquaah, 2005). Agriculture occupies a prime position in the economic system (Opeke 2006). From the foregoing, agriculture is indispensable to the existence of man. According to Ugochukwu (1999), agriculture is the first and most flourishing occupation of mankind. From its early form of wild fruits, leaf, root, snail, insect gathering, fishing, and hunting, to its present mechanized and almost automated form, it has undergone a lot of development. Agriculture is the science or practice of farming, including the cultivation of the soil for the growing of crops and the rearing of animals to provide food, wood, and other products.

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Agricultural Credit:

Agricultural credit is often seen as any of several credit vehicles used to finance agricultural transactions, including loans, notes, bills of exchange, and bankers' acceptances. These types of financing are adapted to the specific financial needs of farmers, which are determined by planting, harvesting, and marketing cycles. Agricultural credit is defined as a process of obtaining control over the use of money and services in the present in exchange for a promise to repay at a future date (Adegeye and Dittoh, 1985). Ijaiya and Abdulraheem (2000) define agricultural credit as a financial resource that is obtainable from the financial institution within a specified period of time based on agreed terms with the promise of paying back as and when due. Also, Osuntogun and Adewunmi (2003) define agricultural credit as the aggregation of agreement where cash and kind contributions are visibly made available to farmers with the obligation of paying back with interest at a later date in the future. In this study, credit to agriculture will be captured with: Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF), foreign aid to agricultural sector (FAA), and commercial banks credit to agricultural sector (CBCAS).

Trade Openness:

Edwards (1998) defines trade openness as the volume of a country's traded sectors in relation to total output. It measures the international competitiveness of a country in the global market (Gwartney, et al., 2001). Trade openness refers to the degree of dependence of an economy on international trade and financial flows (Romer, 1986). Yannikaya (2003) simply define trade openness as an economy's trade intensity. Yanikkaya (2003) opined that this definition has changed over time from one extreme to another in the idea of trade liberalisation. Pritchett (1996) defines trade openness as "that set of policies such that the level and pattern of trade (and prices) are near what they would be under free trade". On the other hand, Krueger (1997) argued that trade openness can be attained by implementing policies that lower the biases against the export sector like subsidising exports or encouraging export schemes. It could be synonymous with the idea of neutrality—the indifference between earning a unit of foreign exchange by exporting and saving a unit through export substitution Harrison (1996) added. It is crucial to understand this definition problem as there are several openness measures that are differently linked to economic growth.

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Agricultural sector output:

According to Oyaniran (2020), agricultural sector performance is measured in terms of the value of production at constant prices and at current prices. It focuses on the measurement of the whole sector (agriculture) and its sub-commodity groups such as crops, livestock, poultry, fisheries, as well as commodities. Tombofa (2004) reported that the state of agriculture is of paramount importance to the development process. The United Nations Organization (2008) estimated that in the world as a whole, over 50% of the world population is engaged in agriculture or dependent on it for a living. Akinboyo (2008) defines agriculture as the science of making use of the land to raise plants and animals. It is the simplification of nature's food webs and the re-channelling of energy for human planting and animal consumption. Ikala (2010) describes agriculture as the profession of the majority of humans. Agricultural sector is the largest sector in the Nigerian economy with its dominant share of the GDP, employment of more than 70% of the active labour force, and the generation of about 88% of non-oil foreign exchange earnings Oji-Okoro (2011).

Conceptual Framework

The study of openness, credit to the agricultural sector, and agricultural sector performance in Nigeria is anchored on three complementary theories such as the factor proportion theory as propounded by Hecksher-Ohlin-Samuelson (H-O-S), the Flying Geese FDI model, and the Mundell-Fleming ISLM model. The postulations of these aforementioned supportive theories are presented in the following framework to explain the relationship between trade openness, foreign direct investment, and the economic performance of the Nigerian economy.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework on the relationship between Openness, Agricultural Credit and Agricultural Output

Source: Authors conceptualization

The conceptual framework for the study of the effect of openness, credit, and agricultural sector output is conceived on the assumption that the openness of an economy entails the viability of the nation's economy or the market share (trade openness and foreign direct investment) will attract foreign physical capital, production techniques, and utilities that tend to impact the domestic enterprises in the host economy both directly and indirectly such as an increase in competition, technological diffusion, an increase in economic efficiency, an increase in consumer choice, and an increase in employment rate, among others (Okonkwo, Egbunike, and Udeh, 2015). The openness

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of the economy also entails collapsing barriers at the national frontier with the aim of ensuring the ease of doing business, which will amount to diversifying the economy from a mono-economy and it is likely to stimulate the import and export of agricultural outputs. On the credit side, it is expected that funds for the agricultural sector will move through three channels: the government, private borrowing, and international aid. These whole packages will be contained in the agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund (ACGSF), foreign aid into agriculture (FAA), and commercial bank credit to agriculture (CBCAS). For agricultural output, when an economy is open, like the Nigerian economy, it attracts an inflow of foreign direct investment.

Theoretical Literature

In this section, the theoretical postulations about openness, credit to agriculture, and agricultural output are explored, beginning with the factor proportion theory as propounded by Hecksher-Ohlin-Samuelson (H-O-S), which was established in 1933. This theory provides an explanation of how free trade leads countries to specialize in the production and export of goods and services that utilize greater quantities of their relatively abundant factors and import goods and services that are relatively scarce.

Mundell (1976) neutralizes the assumption of factor mobility by postulating that trade between two countries takes place at a level at which factor prices tend to equalize in both countries, in absolute as well as relative terms. However, once capital is allowed to move freely across the countries (i.e., from capital-abundant to capital-scarce countries), the difference in factor prices is reduced, while the difference in comparative cost will diminish. Hence, international trade leads to a Pareto-efficient equilibrium that yields higher welfare through its allocation efficiency, which will stimulate agricultural productivity.

Empirical Review

Openness and Agricultural Output

Etuk, Igbodor, and Effiong (2016) used time series data from 1960 to 2014 to estimate variations in agricultural output before and after trade liberalization, as well as the long and short-run effects of agricultural trade policies on agricultural output in Nigeria. The co-integration and error correction model was used to estimate the data. The study

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demonstrated that (i) the mean agricultural output following trade liberalization (AGR GD2) differed from the pre-trade period (AGR GD1). (ii) The t-test result reveals that there is a significant difference in agricultural output between the pre-trade and post-trade liberalization periods as the t_{cal} (4.5146) was greater than the t_{crit} (2.0484) at the 5% level of significance.

Ahungwa, Haruna, Rakiya, and Abdusalam (2014)'s research on "trend analysis of agriculture's contribution to Nigeria's Gross Domestic Product" looked at the trend and contribution of agriculture to Nigeria's GDP from 1960 to 2012. From 1960 to 1975, the study's findings revealed a strong superiority over other industries. A further investigation also showed that an undulating pattern intersected with the industrial sector from 1976 to 1989. On the other hand, the regression results revealed that agriculture contributed significantly to the nation's GDP with a coefficient of 0.664. The cumulative effect of agriculture on GDP clearly demonstrated the sector's dominance in Nigeria's GDP.

Ude and Agodi (2015) used Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (ARCH), Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH), and pairwise gradient causality frameworks to demonstrate a relationship between trade openness and economic growth in their study "Trade Openness makes Sense, using Nigerian Trade Policy as a Yardstick." The interest rate and the exchange rate were discovered to be key factors influencing Nigeria's economic growth rate. The study stated that Nigerian trade policymakers should not only be accountable for developing trade policies but should also consider the policy environment.

Felix, Ukwani, and Martins (2013) conducted a research on the effects of trade liberalization on the Nigerian agricultural industry. The study adopted cointegration and an error correction model. Two models were proposed - the first model captured the impact of trade liberalization on agricultural production in Nigeria, the second model recorded the impact of trade liberalization on the agricultural export subsector in Nigeria. The results of the time-series analysis of the Error Correction Model of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) confirm that agricultural degree of openness and agricultural export to import price ratio were significant in both models; however, agricultural capital formation, the real exchange rate, and foreign investment in agriculture were not significant.

Similarly, Felix, Kolawole, and Musa (2013) used the ordinary least squares

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method to estimate the impact of trade liberalization on economic development in Nigeria (1970–2012) with the goal of investigating the long-term link and structural change that may have occurred with the establishment of a free trade regime in 1986. In the study, trade liberalization was defined as openness and proxied by the ratio of total trade to GDP. The study's findings indicated that liberalization promotes economic growth in Nigeria, with evidence of a long-term link. Strong evidence was discovered to support a structural change that occurred in 1986 with the advent of free trade policies. However, exports were reported to be negatively related to growth. The study concluded by recommending that an enabling environment that will engender further growth, such as a better infrastructural base, adequate financing support, adherence to international best practice in export, and a sound institutional structure, be put in place for sustainability.

Muhammad and Atte (2006) also examined agricultural production in Nigeria with an emphasis on the expansion of the Nigerian economy's agricultural sector. With descriptive statistics and Duncan multiple range test regression analysis as the primary analytical tools and average growth rate, population growth rate, and consumer price index viewed as the most important factors in agricultural domestic output, the findings indicate that Nigerians must pursue trade liberalization policies in order to sustain growth in agriculture and industry.

Agricultural Credit and Agricultural Output

Florence and Nathan (2020) examined the short and long-run impacts of commercial banks' credit on agricultural sector growth. Using quarterly time series data sourced from the Bank of Uganda and the Uganda Bureau of Statistics over the sample period of 2008 Q3–2018 Q4, the study applied the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to examine the short-run and long-term relationship between commercial banks' credit and Uganda's agricultural GDP performance. In the long run, we find credit to have a significant positive impact on agricultural output. Credit for production is found to have a much higher impact on agriculture output compared to credit for processing and marketing. In the short run, we find that bank credit does not have an instantaneous impact on agricultural output. The study provides evidence that commercial banks' agricultural credit contributes significantly to Uganda's agricultural sector GDP. Specifically, the study provides evidence of the segment of agriculture

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where credit has the highest impact. This paper contributes to providing policy options for improving agricultural GDP performance in Uganda, for example, by de-risking the production segment.

Osabohien, Mordi, and Ogundipe (2022) examined how agricultural sector performance will be enhanced in Nigeria through access to credit. The study engaged time series data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and the World Development Indicators (WDI) of the World Bank for the period 198–2018. The Autoregressive Distribution Lag (ARDL) method was used in the analysis. Results showed that agricultural credit proxied by the agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund (ACGSF) and commercial bank credit to agriculture significantly increased agricultural performance by 10.30% and 17.05% respectively. Based on its findings, the study recommended that farmers be provided with sufficient access to credit which will enhance their ability to purchase agricultural inputs required to increase productivity.

Okuneye and Ajayi (2021) examined the effect of commercial banks' credit for agriculture and government agricultural spending on agricultural production in Nigeria between 1980 and 2018. The findings of the ARDL co-integration test revealed that there is a long-term co-movement between agricultural government spending, interest rates, and agricultural production in Nigeria. Increased budgetary allocation to the agricultural sector is also recommended, and a larger proportion of the allocation should be committed to the infrastructural improvement of the sector through the mechanization of the agricultural system in Nigeria.

Gershon, Matthew, Osuagwu, Osabohien, Ekhaton-Mobayode, and Osabuohien (2020) examined the effect of household access to agricultural credit on agricultural production in Nigeria. The study employs the propensity score matching (PSM) technique on data from the Living Standard Measurement Study-Integrated Survey on Agriculture (LSMS-ISA), consisting of 4210 households across the 36 states in Nigeria as well as the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The result of the study shows that households that had access to agricultural credit facilities had yields that were three times those of their counterparts who did not benefit from such facilities. In the event of a shock, the farmers who did not have a source of credit are often forced to adopt measures such as lowering consumption and selling assets, which in the long run worsen their poverty levels.

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The impact of government expenditure and bank credit on domestic agricultural sector output in Nigeria was reviewed. It used the OLS regression analytical method to evaluate the relationship between agricultural output and several factors influencing agricultural productivity in Nigeria such as government expenditure on agriculture, bank loans and advances to agriculture, and an index of agricultural production. Results showed that there existed a negative and significant relationship between government expenditure and agricultural output in Nigeria, while banks credit to agriculture and the index of agricultural production had a positive and significant correlation with agricultural productivity Uremadu, Ehimare, and Okhuebor (2019).

Seven and Tumen (2020) examined the effect of agricultural credit on agricultural output. Employing a combination of panel data and instrumental-variable regression, it was revealed that agricultural credits have a positive impact on agricultural productivity. In particular, doubling agricultural credits generates around a 4-5% increase in agricultural productivity. The study concludes that agricultural credits operate mostly on the agricultural component of GDP in developing countries and agricultural labour productivity in developed countries. Hence, it was recommended that there should be a replacement of the informal credit channel with formal and advanced agricultural credit markets along the development path since it has proven to be the main force driving the labour market response.

Okafor (2020) examined the effect of bank credit on agricultural output in Nigeria, assessed the effect of government expenditure on agricultural output in Nigeria, examined the impact of the Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund on agricultural output in Nigeria, and the effect of interest rates on agricultural output in Nigeria. The research used secondary data collected from the Central Bank of Nigeria's Annual Reports and Statement of accounts. Data were analyzed using econometric techniques such as the Augmented Dickey-Fuller and Philip Perron tests for Unit Roots and the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Technique. The study shows that credit to the agricultural sector, government spending on the agricultural sector, and the agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund have positive and significant effects on agricultural output, while interest rates have a negative and insignificant effect on agricultural output. The study, therefore, concludes that commercial bank credit has a positive effect on agricultural output in Nigeria and has increased agricultural production within the period under review. The study recommends that the government should strengthen the

agricultural credit guarantee scheme through meaningful budgetary allocation to enhance its capital base significantly.

Research Gap

The empirical literature revealed in this study is twofold. We revealed literature relating to trade openness and agricultural output, as well as those relating to agricultural credit to agricultural output. The evidence was mostly similar as the majority of the studies were on the positive side. For instance, Muhammad and Atte (2006), Felix, Kolawole, and Musa (2013), Felix, Ukwani, and Martins (2013), and Etuk, Igbodor, and Effiong (2016); Ahungwa, Haruna, Rakiya, and Abdusalam (2014) used co-integration and error correction models on time series data from 1960 to 2014 to demonstrate that a positive relationship existed between trade openness and agricultural output. Ude and Agodi (2015) used Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (ARCH), Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH), and pairwise gradient causality frameworks to demonstrate that the interest rate and the exchange rate were key factors influencing Nigeria's economic growth rate.

In the second model, literature on the effect of credit on agriculture on agricultural output was looked into by scholars with various results. For instance, Florence and Nathan (2020) used quarterly time series data from 2008 Q3–2018 Q4 and applied the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to show that commercial banks' agricultural credit contributes significantly to Uganda's agricultural sector GDP. Okafor (2020); Bahşi and Etin (2020); Seven and Tumen (2020); Osabohien, Mordi, and Ogundipe (2022) employed Autoregressive Distribution Lag (ARDL) on time series data from 1998–2018 and revealed that agricultural credit proxied by the agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund (ACGSF) and commercial bank credit to agriculture significantly increased agricultural performance. While Okuneye and Ajayi (2021) introduced agricultural government spending, interest rates, and agricultural production in Nigeria, Uremadu, Ehimare, and Okhuebor (2019) reported the existence of a negative and significant relationship between government expenditure and agricultural output in Nigeria.

Gershon, Matthew, Osuagwu, Osabohien, Ekhaton-Mobayode, and Osabuohien (2020) examined the effect of household access to agricultural credit on agricultural production in Nigeria. The result of the study shows that households that had access to

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agricultural credit facilities had yields that were three times those of their counterparts who did not benefit from such facilities.

Among the studies revealed, scholars have predicted the presence of a positive relationship between trade openness and agricultural sector output, as well as agricultural credit and agricultural output. The methods used for the study include error correction mechanisms, autoregressive and distributed lag (ARDL), Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (ARCH), Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH), and pairwise gradient causality frameworks. On conceptual grounds, this study departed from other studies by looking at the openness of an economy as the ability to attract foreign direct investment into it and promote market viability, while credit to the agricultural sector will be seen from three dimensions: government intervention (Agricultural credit guarantee scheme funding), private borrowing (commercial bank credit to agriculture), and international development assistance (foreign aid into agriculture). Aside from the above, this study extended the scope of the literature by looking at the aforesaid relationship from 1981 to 2021 to capture the current developments in Nigeria, where food importation has become the new normal.

Methodology

The theoretical basis for this macro-econometric model is hinged on Hecksher-Ohlin-Samuelson (H-O-S) and Mundell (1976). The procedure for modeling agricultural sector output is based on the agricultural output model that will be built on the ratio of the sectors contributions to Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The study estimated two structural equations of agricultural sector output separately, using the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and bounds cointegrations test, which was established by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith in 2001. The justification for the choice of the ARDL model is premised on the mixed order of integration of the time series data as exposed by the Phillip and Perron unit root test. To ensure that the estimators were BLUE, we conducted a series of post-estimation tests such as the normality of the residual test, the serial correlation test, the heteroskedasticity test, the model misspecification test, and the model stability test.

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Model Specification

This study adopts the modified version of Etuk, Igbodor, and Effiong (2017) analysis of trade liberalization policies on agricultural output growth in Nigeria for the period of 1986 to 2014. The linear expression of their model is expressed below:

$$\text{LnAGDP} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{LnOPT} + \beta_2 \text{LnINT} + \beta_3 \text{LnEXCH} + \beta_4 \text{LnCPI} + \beta_5 \text{LnGOVI} + u_{i1}$$

Where;

Ln = Natural log of numbers to base

AGDP = Index of Agricultural output (GDP) in Nigeria at time t

Opt = Degree of openness which is export plus import divided by GDP. It is used as a proxy for trade liberalization

INT = Real interest rate

EXCH = Exchange rate which represent a proxy of exchange rate prices at time t

CPI = consumer price index

GOVI = government investment

DUM = which take the value of 1 in the SAP period and 0 in the rest of the period.

Whereas, the modified version of the equation will retain agricultural sector contribution to GDP as the dependent variable, the independent variable becomes trade openness (TOP), foreign direct investment (FDI), and exchange rate (EXR).

Model One: Openness and Agricultural output.

The functional form of the equation is expressed as:

$$\text{AGDP} = f(\text{TOP}, \text{FDIA}, \text{EXR}) \quad 2$$

While the log-linear form of the relationship becomes

$$\text{AGDP}_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{TOP}_t + \beta_2 \text{FDIA}_t + \beta_3 \text{EXR}_t + \mu_t \quad 3$$

Where:

AGDP_t = Agricultural Output at time t.

FDIA_t = Foreign Direct Investment into Agriculture at time t.

EXR_t = Exchange Rate at time t.

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β 's = Unknown Parameters

α = Constant term

a priori expectation, $\beta_1, \beta_2, >0$ while $\beta_3 <0$

Model Two: Credit to Agricultural Sector and Agricultural Output

This research work will adopt the modified version of Okafor (2020), who modeled the effect of commercial bank credit on agricultural development in Nigeria.

The model is estimated as thus:

$$AGO = f(CAS, GSA, ACGS, INTR) \quad 3.1$$

$$AGO = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CAS + \beta_2 GSA + \beta_3 ACGS + \beta_4 INTR \quad 3.2$$

Where:

AGO = Agricultural output at time t

CAS = Credit to Agricultural Sector at time t

GSA = Government Spending on Agricultural Sector at time t

ACGS = Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund at time t

INTR = Interest Rate

β_0 and μ are the constant and error term respectively while $\beta_1, \beta_2,$ and β_3 are the coefficients of agricultural output, credit to agricultural sector, government spending on agricultural sector, agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund on the agricultural sector, and interest rate on agricultural output.

The function expression of our model goes thus:

$$AGODP = f(ACGSF, GEA, DMBCAS, INTR) \quad 3.1$$

$$AGDP = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ACGSF + \beta_2 FAA + \beta_3 CBCA + \beta_4 INTR \quad 3.2$$

Where:

AGDP = Agricultural output at time t

DMBCAS = Deposit Money Banks Credit to Agricultural Sector at time t

GEA = Government Expenditure on Agriculture time t

ACGSF = Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund at time t

INTR = Interest Rate at time t

β_0 = Constant

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 = Coefficients to be estimated

μ = error term

a priori $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 >$ while $\beta_4 <0$

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Description of Variables

Dependent Variable:

Agricultural GDP (AGDP): Productivity measures the quantity of output produced with a given quantity of inputs. Long-term productivity growth reflects improvements in farmers' production efficiency and technological progress.

Independent Variables

Trade Openness (TOP): Trade openness is defined as the ratio of exports and imports over GDP. The more favourable a country's trade openness is, the lower the level of poverty.

Agricultural GDP (AGDP): Output is measured as an aggregate index of crops, livestock, wool, dairy, and other farm income; input is measured as an aggregate index of land, capital, labour, materials, and services. It is the ratio of agriculture to GDP in Nigeria.

Deposit Money Banks Credit to the Agricultural Sector (DMBCAS): This is also known as the Commercial Agriculture Credit Scheme (CACCS). Agricultural credit refers to one of several credit vehicles used to finance agricultural transactions such as a loan, note, bill of exchange, or banker's acceptance.

Government Expenditure on Agriculture (GEA): Government spending on agriculture is the sum of current, capital, and recurrent expenditure on agriculture over the study period.

Agricultural Credit Guarantee Scheme Fund (ACGSF): The Fund guarantees credit facilities extended to farmers by banks up to 75% of the amount in default net of any security realized.

Interest Rate (INT): An interest rate is the amount of interest due per period as a proportion of the amount lent, deposited, or borrowed (called the principal sum).

Foreign Direct Investment into Agriculture (FDIA): Foreign direct investment into agriculture is the aid that comes from overseas and is directed into the agricultural sector.

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Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Exchange Rate (EXR): This is the rate at which the currency of one country will be exchanged with those of other countries.

Analysis of Data:

Descriptive statistics

	AGDP	ACGSF	FDIA	GEA	DMBCAS	EXR	TOP	INT
Mean	8511.762	3114251.	1.522417	15192.07	179.3681	110.8405	46.27244	17.30987
Median	2015.422	728545.4	1.099403	7064.500	48.56150	112.0252	48.45000	17.50000
Maximum	41126.06	12456251	5.790847	43500.00	1111.154	390.2093	81.81000	29.80000
Minimum	17.05218	24654.90	0.257422	12.80000	0.590600	0.610000	21.12000	7.750000
Std. Dev.	11183.50	3883011.	1.208559	16288.35	272.8429	100.9339	18.84347	4.637785
Skewness	1.378496	0.943567	1.830233	0.515875	1.788187	0.863969	0.031469	0.269227
Kurtosis	4.007211	2.426742	6.428508	1.549983	5.453557	3.216297	1.662978	3.517521
JarqueBera	14.71810	6.645245	42.97086	5.410393	32.13443	5.180618	3.060633	0.952843
Probability	0.000637	0.036058	0.000000	0.066857	0.000000	0.074997	0.216467	0.621002
Sum	348982.2	1.28E+08	62.41909	622874.7	7354.091	4544.460	1897.170	709.7048
Sum Sq. Dev.	5.00E+09	6.03E+14	58.42456	1.06E+10	2977729.	407505.8	14203.06	860.3621
Observations	41	41	41	41	41	41	41	41

The averages of the series, AGDP, ACGSF, FDIA, GEA, DMBCAS EXR, TOP, and INT are 8511.762, 3114251, 1.522417, 15192.07, 179.3681, 110.8405, 46.27244, and 17.30987, while the median values are 2015.422, 728545.4, 1.099403, 7064.500, 48.56150, 112.0252, 48.45000, and 17.50000. The disparity or dispersion of the mean values of AGDP, ACGSF, FDI, GEA, and CBCAS from their mean values shows how weak the variables are at stimulating growth in the long run. The skewness values of all the variables show that they have long right tails, while the kurtosis values of 1.549983 and 1.662978 for GEA and TOP were platykurtic relative to the normal distribution. The kurtosis of 2.426742 for ACGSF was mesokurtic, while others were leptokurtic. Finally, the Jacque-Bera statistic and its probability value showed a normal distribution for GEA, EXR, TOP, and INT, while others did not have a normally distributed residual.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Table 2: Stationarity Test (Philip Perron)

Variables	Level		1 st Difference		Order
	T-Stat.	5% Critical Value	T-Stat.	5% Critical Value	
LOG(AGDP)	-0.187053	-3.526609	-4.190734	-3.529758	I(1)
LOG(ACGSF)	-0.576338	-3.526609	-5.728266	-3.529758	I(1)
LOG(DMBCAS)	-2.432968	-3.526609	-4.205004	-3.526609	I(1)
EXR	-2.990079	-3.526609	-6.435903	-3.529758	I(1)
LOG(FDIA)	-3.555958	-2.936942	-	-	I(0)
LOG(GEA)	-0.172593	-3.526609	-7.114351	-3.529758	I(1)
TOP	-2.008335	-3.526609	-11.54347	-3.529758	I(1)
INT	-3.363318	-2.936942	-	-	I(0)

Source: Authors compilation from Eview-10.05

The summary table for the stationarity test conducted by a unit root approach proposed by Philip and Perron (1988) is shown in Table 2. The summary result shows that almost all the variables in the study were stationary at level except the log of foreign direct investment (FDIA) and interest rate. By implication, those series became stationary at level, while others became stationary after they were subjected to the first difference. According to Box and Jenkins (1987), as cited in Hagan and Behr (1987), non-stationary time series data will be subjected to first differencing to make them stationary. This justified the adoption of the cointegration approach developed by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001). The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model bounds test for cointegration houses a cointegration test known as the bounds test for cointegration. The bounds test helps to ascertain the presence or absence of a long-run relationship among time series data by comparing the F-statistic value with the upper bounds critical value of 5%. The ARDL model is useful for forecasting and disentangling long-run relationships from short-run dynamics.

IJCITR

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Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Assumptions

- i. The absence of autocorrelation is the very first requirement of ARDL.
- ii. There should not be any heteroscedasticity in the data.
- iii. The data should follow a normal distribution.
- iv. Data should be stationary either on $I(0)$ or $I(1)$ or on both.

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag model (ARDL (p,q)) assumes that a time series $\text{LOG}(\text{AGDP})$ can be represented by a linear function of p of its lagged values of $\text{LOG}(\text{AGDP}(-1))$ and q of the lags of another time series X_{t-1} . Long-run relationship: Some time series are bound together due to equilibrium forces, even though the individual time series might move considerably. If both the F and t statistics of the bounds test are significant, only then can we conclude that the variables are cointegrated; otherwise, they are not. For performing the ARDL bounds test, at least 30 observations (for yearly data) are required; otherwise, the estimation becomes biased.

Bounds Cointegration Test for Model One

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	k
F-statistic	4.720109	3

Table 3: Critical Value Bounds

Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.72	3.77
5%	3.23	4.35
2.5%	3.69	4.89
1%	4.29	5.61

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Table 3 depicts the bounds of cointegration in the agricultural output model. The adoption of the bounds cointegration test after the lag length of the model has been estimated became necessary since it shows the presence or otherwise of a cointegrating relationship among the variables. The bounds cointegration test shows that a long-run cointegrating relationship existed among the variables in the model and that such a relationship has necessitated the need to estimate the short- and long-run output. This is premised on the fact that the f-statistic value of 4.720109 is greater than the upper bound critical value of 4.35. To this end, therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Short Run Result for Model One

Cointegrating Form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DLOG(AGDP(-1))	0.209177	0.151262	1.382884	0.1760
D(TOP)	-0.001968	0.001801	-1.092464	0.2825
DLOG(FDIA)	0.044189	0.037823	1.168302	0.2511
DLOG(EXR)	-0.120953	0.050467	2.396656	0.0224
CointEq(-1)	-0.106896	0.038611	-2.768517	0.0092

$$\text{Cointeq} = \text{LOG(AGDP)} - (-0.0184*\text{TOP} + 0.4134*\text{LOG(FDI)} + 1.1315$$

$$*\text{LOG(EXR)} + 5.0966)$$

R-squared	0.897422	Mean dependent var	7.525062
Adjusted R-squared	0.897031	S.D. dependent var	2.388492
S.E. of regression	0.130140	Akaike info criterion	-1.099776
Sum squared resid	0.558900	Schwarz criterion	-0.843844
Log likelihood	27.44564	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.007950
F-statistic	25.53405	Durbin-Watson stat	1.925184
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleliv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

In the short run, the R-squared value is 0.897422, while the adjusted R-squared value is 0.897031. By implication, 89 percent of the variations in Agricultural output are associated with trade openness and credit to the agricultural sector in Nigeria, while the remaining 11 percent is captured in the error term. The robustness of the model as expressed by the f-statistic of 25.53405 and its corresponding probability value of 0.000000 shows that the model has a good fit. The Akaike information criterion, valued at -1.099776, is the best for the model since it has the lowest value. The error correction term appeared with the normal sign and was significant at 5 percent. By implication, the past disequilibrium will herald a long-run equilibrium at a speed of -0.106896 (11%) annually.

The past realization of the dependent variable has a positive effect on the dependent variable, but it is not statistically significant enough to cause variation in the dependent variable in the short run. Similarly, the coefficient of trade openness has a negative effect on the dependent variable, but it is insignificant enough to cause any deviation in the movement of agricultural output in Nigeria. Comparatively, the coefficients of openness of the Nigerian economy, which measure market size, do not contribute to agricultural output growth in Nigeria, and the possible reason for such a development could be that the nation exports less of its agricultural produce due to its large population of consumers. Centrality: the coefficient of the exchange rate has a negative effect on the dependent variable and is significant at 5 percent. An appreciation of the exchange rate will amount to a 0.120953 (12%) decrease in agricultural output in Nigeria, *ceteris paribus*. This causation is consistent with the *priori* expectation or economic theory because, when the local currency depreciates in value due to a hike in the exchange rate, it will increase the cost of production, reduce investment, and result in a reduction in output. This is a truth in Nigeria: since 1985, when the structural adjustment program was introduced, the value of the local currency has passed through several phases of devaluations to the extent that it has been ridiculed in African markets.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Long Run Result for Model Two

Long Run Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
TOP	-0.018408	0.013860	-1.328132	0.1932
LOG(FDIA)	0.413385	0.387283	1.067397	0.2935
LOG(EXR)	-1.131502	0.122775	9.216035	0.0000
C	5.096630	0.881204	5.783714	0.0000

In the long run, the coefficient of trade openness has a negative effect on the dependent variable, while that of foreign direct investment has a positive influence on the dependent variable. Yet, they are not significant enough to cause any change in the dependent variable. Similarly, to the short-run result, the coefficient of the exchange rate has a negative effect on the dependent variable and it is statistically significant to cause variation in the dependent variable. A percentage increase in the exchange rate will amount to a 1.131502 (1.13%) reduction in agricultural output in the long run. This implies that the continued decrease in agricultural output in Nigeria is associated with the hike in the dollar-to-naira exchange rate. Hence, we conclude that the exchange rate has a permanent negative influence on the agricultural sector in Nigeria, and this conforms to economic theory.

Post Estimation Test for model one

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Table 1 illustrates the post-estimation test for the study of openness, agricultural credit, and agricultural output in Nigeria for the period spanning 1981 and 2021. The essence of the post-estimation test is to ensure that the estimation procedure does not violate the basic OLS assumption. Hence, five post-estimation tests were considered for the estimated ARDL (2, 0, 0, 0). Starting with the normality of the residual test, the evidence above shows that the residuals are normally distributed since the Jarque-Bera statistic value of 3.780731 is within the minimal value, and the probability value of 0.151017 is less than the required minimum of 0.05. Therefore, the assumption of normality of the residual is adhered to.

S/N	TEST DESCRIPTION	T.STAT	PROB.	F.STAT	PROB.	REMARKS
1	Normality of the Residual Test.	3.780731	0.151017			Accepted
2	Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:	1.300128	0.2865	2.930904	0.2310	Accepted
3	Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	1.458815	0.2363	5.712909	0.2216	Accepted
4	Ramsey RESET Test	0.753182	0.4567	0.567283	0.4567	Accepted
5	Cusum Test	Normal		Normal		Accepted

Source: Author's compilation from EViews 10.

Secondly, the serial independence assumption was upheld since both the t-statistics and f-statistics values of 1.300128 and 2.930904 have probability values of 0.2865 and 0.2310, which are higher than the threshold of 0.05. Thirdly, the assumption of homoscedasticity of the least squares estimate was upheld with Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity t-statistic and f-statistic values of 1.458815 and 5.712909 with probability values of 0.2363 and 0.2216. Fourthly, issues of model misspecification were addressed with the Ramsey Reset Test. The test statistics show that the model is moderately specified correctly since the joint probability values of the t-statistic of 0.753182 and the f-statistic of 0.567283 are 0.4567.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Finally, the test for model stability was conducted using recursive ordering, or the cusum plot. The cusum plot shows that the estimated model falls within the required interval and should be accepted. To this end, we conclude that the classical least squares assumption is not violated in the estimation of the effect of openness on agriculture in Nigeria.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Model Two

Bounds Cointegration Test of Model Two

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	k
F-statistic	4.625110	4

Critical Value Bounds

Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
2.5%	3.25	4.49
1%	3.74	5.06

Table 8 depicts the bounds of cointegration in credit to agriculture and the agricultural output model. The adoption of the bounds cointegration test after the lag length of the model has been estimated and it became necessary since it shows the presence or otherwise of a cointegrating relationship among the variables. The bounds cointegration test shows that a long-run cointegrating relationship existed among the variables in the model and that such a relationship has necessitated the need to estimate the short and long-run output. This is premised on the fact that the f-statistic value of 4.625110 is greater than the upper bound critical value of 4.01. To this end, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Short Run Result

Cointegrating Form

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
DLOG(AGDP(-1))	0.455774	0.148408	3.071099	0.0048
DLOG(ACGSF)	-0.061200	0.046020	-1.329871	0.1947
DLOG(GEA)	0.181077	0.064505	2.807156	0.0092
DLOG(GEA(-1))	0.154943	0.065832	-2.353611	0.0261
DLOG(DMBCAS)	0.042070	0.077335	0.543992	0.5909
D(INT)	-0.000901	0.005953	-0.151392	0.8808
CointEq(-1)	-0.405731	0.094743	-4.282447	0.0002

$$\text{Cointeq} = \text{LOG}(\text{AGDP}) - (0.0327 * \text{LOG}(\text{ACGSF}) + 0.5673 * \text{LOG}(\text{GEA}) + 0.3679 * \text{LOG}(\text{DMBCAS}) - 0.0333 * \text{INT} + 1.9010)$$

R-squared	0.898468	Mean dependent var	7.525062
Adjusted R-squared	0.887844	S.D. dependent var	2.388492
S.E. of regression	0.110903	Akaike info criterion	-1.312660
Sum squared resid	0.332086	Schwarz criterion	-0.800795
Log likelihood	37.59687	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-1.129007
F-statistic	15.99873	Durbin-Watson stat	1.875003
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

In the short run, the R-squared value is 0.898468, while the adjusted R-squared value is 0.887844. By implication, 89 percent of the variations in agricultural output are associated with the credit given to the agricultural sector in Nigeria, while the remaining 11 percent is captured in the error term. The robustness of the model as expressed by the f-statistic of 15.99873 and its corresponding probability value of 0.000000 shows that the model has a good fit. The Akaike information criterion valued at -1.312660 is the

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

best for the model since it has the lowest value. The error correction term appeared with the normal sign and was significant at 5 percent. The Durbin-Watson stat value of 1.875003 suggests the absence of serial correlation in the residual. By implication, the past disequilibrium will herald a long-run equilibrium at a speed of -0.405731 (41%) annually.

In the short run, the coefficient of the past value of the dependent variable, $DLOG(AGDP(-1))$, has a positive influence on the dependent variable and it is statistically significant at 5%. Therefore, an increase in the past value of agricultural output will amount to a 0.455774 (46%) increase in the current output. By implication, the agricultural sector has a feed-back effect on itself, and that gives robustness to the short-run dynamics. Contrarily, the coefficient of the agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund $DLOG(ACGSF)$ has a negative effect on the dependent variable but not significant at 5 percent. This also means that the scheme does not contribute to the short-term growth of the sector in Nigeria. Evidence drawn from the table shows that government expenditure on agricultural sector has a positive effect on the dependent variable (agricultural output) and it is significant at 5 percent. Therefore, a percentage increase in government expenditure in agriculture will amount to a 0.181077 (18%) increase in agricultural output in Nigeria. The implication of this is that government expenditure contributes 18 percent to the total productivity of the sector. This assertion exposed the significance of sectoral aid to the nation's pace for food security, and it does conform to theoretical expectations. Corroborating this view is the lag value of foreign aid, with a 0.154943 positive effect on the dependent variable. Contrarily, the coefficient of commercial banks credit to agriculture has a positive effect on the dependent variable but it is insignificant at 5 percent, while the coefficient of interest rate, which has a negative effect, does not have a significant influence on the dependent variable either. Hence, we assert that loans from commercial banks are not drivers of the agricultural sector in Nigeria, and such an anomaly could be attributed to the hike in interest rates.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Long Run Result

Long Run Coefficients

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOG(ACGSF)	0.032725	0.065985	0.495940	0.6239
LOG(GEA)	0.567302	0.102711	5.523300	0.0000
LOG(CBCAS)	0.367906	0.111243	3.307231	0.0027
INT	-0.033315	0.016970	-1.963200	0.0600
C	1.900999	0.654712	2.903567	0.0073

In the long run, the coefficient of the agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund, LOG (ACGSF) has a positive effect on the dependent variable, but not significant at 5%. While the coefficient of foreign aid, LOG (GEA), has a positive effect on the dependent variable as expected and it is significant at 5%, a percentage increase in government expenditure on agriculture will, all things being equal, amount to a 0.567302 (57%) increase in agricultural output in Nigeria. The implication of such a positive relationship is that government expenditure affects agricultural output mainly, and the utilization has yielded fruits despite the insecurity in the northern part of the country. Similarly, the coefficient of deposit money banks credit to agriculture influenced agricultural output by 0.367906 (36%) in the long run. This explains the far-reaching positive effect of local banks credit on agricultural investments in Nigeria, as expected.

Post Estimation Test for model Two

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Elevis Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Table 1 illustrates the post-estimation test for the study of agricultural credit and agricultural output in Nigeria for the period spanning 1981 and 2021. The essence of the post-estimation test is to ensure that the estimation procedure does not violate the basic OLS assumption. Hence, five post-estimation tests were considered for the estimated ARDL (2, 1, 2, 1, and 1). Starting with the normality of the residual test, the evidence above shows that the residuals are normally distributed since the Jarque-Bera statistic value of 1.349898 is within the minimal value, while the probability value of 0.509182 is less than the required minimum of 0.05. Therefore, the assumption of normality of the residual is adhered to.

S/N	TEST DESCRIPTION	T.STAT	PROB.	F.STAT	PROB.	REMARKS
1	Normality of the Residual Test.	1.349898	0.509182			Accepted
2	Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:			0.046972		
3	Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	0.016882	0.9833	3.022062	0.9768	Accepted
4	Ramsey RESET Test	0.314991	0.9542	0.706940	0.9330	Accepted
5	Cusum Test	0.840797	0.4073	Normal	0.4073	Accepted

Source: Authors compilation from EViews 10.

Secondly, the serial independence assumption was upheld since both the t-statistics and f-statistics values of 0.016882 and 0.046972 have probability values of 0.9833 and 0.9768, which are higher than the threshold of 0.05. Thirdly, the assumption of homoscedasticity of the least squares estimate was upheld with Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey; heteroskedasticity t-statistic and f-statistic values of 0.314991 and 3.022062 with probability values of 0.95423 and 0.9330. Fourthly, issues of model misspecification were addressed with the Ramsey Reset Test. The test statistics show that the model is moderately specified correctly since the joint probability values of the t-statistic of 0.840797 and the f-statistic of 0.706940 are 0.4073.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

Finally, the test for model stability was conducted using recursive ordering, or the cusum plot. The cusum plot shows that the estimated model falls within the required interval and should be accepted. To this end, we conclude that the classical least squares assumption is not violated in the estimation of the effect of agricultural credits on agriculture output in Nigeria.

Summary and Conclusion

The study examined the effect of openness and credit to the agricultural sector on its contribution to Gross Domestic Product in Nigeria using the Autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and bound test approach. The data was sourced from 1981 to 2021. The unit root test shows that the variables had a mixed order of integration. The long-run analyses of the estimate found that openness does not have a significant effect on

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Eleliv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

agricultural output in both the long run and short run, while the exchange rate had a deleterious effect on agricultural output as was expected in the first equation. These contradicts the positive relationship that was estimated by scholars like Muhammad and Atte (2006), Felix, Kolawole, and Musa (2013), Felix, Ukweni, and Martins (2013), Ahungwa, Haruna, Rakiya, and Abdusalam (2014); and the possible reason for such anomaly could be that the nation imports more than she exports, making her net export on goods and service negative all the time. Secondly, it may be that, the foreign direct investment into agriculture is not sufficient to stimulate growth in the sector due to volatility of the exchange rate and insecurity in northern Nigeria where farming is mostly done.

In the second equation, while noting that the past realization of agricultural output has a growth effect on the current value, government expenditure on agriculture has a positive effect on agriculture in both the long run and the short run as deposit money banks credit only influences the sector positively in the long run. The positive attribute of government expenditure in agricultural sector was possible because government send farm input directly to farmers in many cases. If these funds go directly into the hands of these farmers, they will divert them for conspicuous consumption.

The long-run significant effect of deposit money banks credit to agriculture, as estimated, means that the fund invested in farming takes more time to yield the expected result. But farmers in Nigeria find it difficult to get loans from deposit money banks, and the few that do get them are either relatives of bankers or members of cooperative societies. Deposit money banks on the other hand, charge a monthly interest rate for their loans, and farm produce is in season, making it impossible to meet monthly repayment plans. This supports the views of Florence and Nathan (2020); Okafor (2020); Bahşi and Etin (2020); Seven and Tumen (2020); Osabohien, Mordi, and Ogundipe (2022) who used quarterly time series data from 2008 Q3–2018 Q4 and applied the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to show that commercial banks' agricultural credit contributes significantly to agricultural sector GDP.

Recommendations

- i. To boost the agricultural sector, the government should improve trade liberalization and focus on exporting agricultural commodities to attain a wider market.

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Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

Dr. Edward Wasurum

VOLUME 1, ISSUE 1, SEPTEMBER, 2023

ISSN: 3026-9733

- ii. To boost agricultural output, the government should increase funding for the agricultural credit guarantee scheme fund (ACGSF) and allow rural farmers access to funding.
- iii. The government should ensure that foreign aid to the sector is used to purchase agricultural inputs that would be delivered directly to farmers, and they should monitor their uses.
- iv. Efforts should be made to reduce the devaluation of the local currency as the exchange rate appreciates.
- v. The government should encourage citizens to continue to patronize local agricultural output to enable farmers to reinvest their proceeds into the system.

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